

A Landscape Analysis of Health Data in Canada

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Introduction

The World Data System (WDS), an international organization dedicated to promoting long-term stewardship and advocating for access to quality scientific data, recognizes the critical importance of data sharing for health research. The COVID-19 pandemic underscored this need, catalyzing an unprecedented demand for rapid health data sharing. The ability to quickly analyze data from diverse sources, such as electronic health records (EHRs), genomic data, population health surveillance data, and research-generated data, proved crucial for understanding the virus, developing treatments, and informing public health interventions. This experience highlighted the importance of having health data that is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) to effectively address global health challenges.

A robust and interconnected digital health ecosystem is essential to support these efforts. This report, prepared to inform the WDS's understanding of the Canadian context, will map the roles and relationships of key contributing organizations, both nationally and provincially, within the Canadian health data landscape. It will highlight identifiable essential data repository attributes where applicable and provide recommendations for future development and collaboration. While data repositories play a significant role, this analysis expands to include organizations and systems that facilitate data access, research, and policy development.

Ultimately, this report will provide a comprehensive overview of the Canadian digital health data landscape, facilitating a deeper understanding of its complexities and identifying opportunities for advancement within the context of the WDS's global mission.

Canadian Health Data Landscape

This analysis section will review numerous health data repositories and related entities at both the national/pan-Canadian and provincial levels. The organizations included are based on prior knowledge or searches using re3data.org, a global registry of research data repositories covering all disciplines [1], and the Google search engine.

Each review will include:

- a description of the health data entity or repository,
- characterization of the intended users/audience,
- identification of partners and supporting institutions.

The health data repository reviews will also include:

- details on data accessibility,
- re3data confirmation.

Pan-Canadian Data Entities

Canadian Institute for Health Information (CIHI) Repository

The Canadian Institute for Health Information (CIHI) is an independent, non-profit organization with a mandate to provide essential information to support evidence-based decision-making in healthcare [2]. To achieve this goal, CIHI partially functions as a national repository, aggregating data reported by health authorities and health providers across Canada [2]. The scope of data holdings encompasses a broad spectrum of health information, including types of care, population-specific data (First Nations, child/youth, seniors), healthcare quality, health conditions and outcomes, and a comprehensive overview of the health system [3].

CIHI collaborates extensively with all federal and provincial governments, and the primary data depositors, health authorities and health facilities, alongside other partners across Canada and globally [2]. This has established CIHI as a central hub for Canadian health data. Thus, while the primary intended audience for CIHI's data includes health researchers from Canadian health facilities, universities, and other public research institutions, other researchers from private or foreign organizations can also use the data [4].

Data accessibility at CIHI varies. Some high-level aggregated data tables are freely available for download [5]. However, the majority of CIHI's holdings are made accessible to researchers through a data request process and a secure access environment [4]. These access methods incur hourly recovery costs, which vary based on client type, such as public sector researchers versus private and foreign researchers [4]. Notably, requests for identifiable Indigenous data require explicit approval from the relevant First Nations, Inuit, or Métis authorities, reflecting CIHI's commitment to the OCAP (Ownership, Control, Access, and Possession) principles [4].

Researchers across Canada and the globe can discover CIHI's data through the re3data registry listing [6]. The entry includes many essential metadata fields, such as the repository name, a description, the repository type, the hosting institution, type of institution, policy details, types of data access and deposits permitted, and an indication that data quality management procedures exist [6]. However, other important metadata fields are not included, such as using a persistent identifier system, having a versioning process, or evidence of certification or compliance with a repository standard [6].

Canadian Health Information Management Association (CHIMA)

The Canadian Health Information Management Association (CHIMA) is a national non-profit professional association that plays a significant role within the Canadian health data ecosystem [7] CHIMA does not directly manage or operate any data repositories. Instead, the organization focuses on supporting health information management professionals, including medical coding specialists, health policy researchers, patient records managers, and database/data administrators [7,8]

CHIMA's contributions to the health data landscape are primarily through advocacy, community building, monitoring of industry trends, and providing professional development and employment opportunities [7]. CHIMA operates alongside the Canadian College of Health Information Management, a non-profit organization that provides accreditation and certifications to health information management professionals [7]. CHIMA also maintains a network of partnerships across industry, community, academic, and government sectors, including organizations such as Canada Health Infoway, CIHI, McMaster University, University of Victoria, Bell, EY, and Esri Canada.[9]

Canada Health Infoway

Canada Health Infoway is a non-profit organization, funded by the federal government, primarily focused on improving equitable access to health services for all Canadians through digital health innovations [9]. While not a traditional data repository, Infoway plays a significant role in advancing interoperability within the Canadian health data ecosystem. This is achieved through initiatives such as the pan-Canadian Interoperability Roadmap, a framework aimed at establishing a connected care system, and the development of the pan-Canadian Patient Summary Specification [9].

Infoway primarily focuses on addressing clinical challenges within the healthcare system. However, it also supports the health research community by partnering with researchers and making data from major national studies FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) [10]. To facilitate data sharing, Infoway utilizes a small repository within the University of Victoria's Dataverse collection, where data from surveys on Canadian Physicians and Nurses and the Canadian Digital Health Surveys are made available for any researchers interested in analyzing the resulting data from these surveys [11].

The data in this repository is freely downloadable for all users who agree to the terms of use, restrictions, conditions, and disclaimers [11]. While Infoway does not have an individual entry in the re3data registry, its host, the University of Victoria's Dataverse collection, does have a re3data entry [12]. This listing includes important metadata, such as the use of a persistent identifier system, data accessibility details, links to the data policies, information on the metadata standards used, the existence of data versioning features, and confirmation that the repository is certified with the CoreTrust Seal [12].

Canadian Open Neuroscience Platform (CONP) Portal

The Canadian Open Neuroscience Platform (CONP) Portal functions as both a repository and a data-sharing initiative within the Canadian neuroscience community [13]. It began as a project initially funded by the Brain Canada Foundation, with the principal investigator from McGill and team members from various academic and research institutions across Canada [14].

Presently, the data portal is managed by the Canadian Open Neuroscience Platform, a national network of neuroscience research centers that collaborate on various open neuroscience initiatives [15]. The funders are organizations such as the Brain Canada Foundation, the Ontario

Brain Institute, the Quebec Bio-imaging Network, UBC, and the University of Calgary [16]. Additionally, CONP also collaborates with various partners. These include academic institutions, such as Dalhousie and the University of Alberta, and research institutes, such as the Djavad Mowafaghian Centre for Brain Health and the Centre for Addiction and Mental Health (CAMH) [17]. The primary users and contributors to CONP are academic and research institutes, with most datasets sourced from Canadian neuroscience research institutes [13]. Data is available to anyone interested in neuroscience research [18].

Functionally, the data portal is a decentralized, federated system for FAIR sharing of neuroscience data and relevant tools and pipelines [19]. While primarily containing neuroimaging data, CONP Portal also supports transcriptomics, genomics, and other related data modalities [13]. To facilitate the processing of large datasets requiring high-performance computing, the portal is integrated with CBRAIN, an open-source web-based platform by the McGill Centre for Integrative Neuroscience, for improving data accessibility, management, and processing of large neuroimaging datasets [20]. A key objective of the CONP Portal is to enable researchers to gain valuable insights by linking datasets that are typically siloed and consolidating comparable small datasets to enhance the scientific validity of their studies [19].

Data accessibility within the CONP Portal is determined by the data author/submitter, offering flexibility in how data is shared [21]. Options include direct download from the CONP Portal, download through DataLad, an open-source data management tool, access via CBRAIN, or off-site download controlled by the owner, typically requiring an external data access request [18]. The original data owners maintain ownership, copyright, and data licensing. Data sharing is designed to be distributed, automated, and simple while adhering to the FAIR principles [13]. Anyone can share data by providing the required files—a `readme.md` containing a general description of the dataset and other relevant details, and a `data.json` file containing the metadata—and optionally a logo image, using one of the storage providers: Zenodo, OSF, CONP's internal server, or through Datalad and Github [22].

CONP has a re3data entry, which specifies the type of accesses and uploads permitted, data licenses used, the use of a persistent identifier system and the inclusion of data versioning [23]. However, the data quality management process is unknown, and there is no evidence of the repository being certified or supporting specific metadata standards [23].

Data Access Support Hub (DASH)

The Data Access Support Hub (DASH) is a data access portal designed and managed by the Health Research Data Network Canada (HRDN), serving as a single access and support point for multi-jurisdictional and national health research [24]. HRDN is a network of federal, provincial, and territorial data centers focused on sharing knowledge, fostering collaboration, and driving innovation while respecting public expectations and Indigenous data sovereignty [25], [26].

Unlike a traditional repository, DASH does not hold data itself [24]. Instead, it harmonizes the process of accessing multiple data repositories and supports parallel and federated analysis

work [24]. These member organizations and data repositories include [CIHI](#), [Health Data Nova Scotia](#), [Health Research Data Platform Saskatchewan](#), [Institute for Clinical Evaluative Science](#), [Manitoba Centre for Health Policy](#), [Population Data BC](#), and [Secure Island Data Repository](#).

DASH is government-funded through the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR) and serves all researchers conducting multi-regional health-related research in Canada [25]. While there is no charge for the services offered by the DASH team, each member organization may have data access fees that researchers are required to pay [27]. These fees vary widely based on the provided analytic services and project complexity, ranging from approximately \$5,000 to \$45,000 per HRDN member [27].

The process of accessing data through DASH typically involves three phases:

1. Researchers create a DASH account and complete an intake form. The DASH team then coordinates a project feasibility and costing review with the researchers and relevant data centers.
2. With support from the DASH team, the researcher completes a single data access request form.
3. Researchers are invoiced for access costs and gain access to the requested data. With approvals, researchers are able to link two internal or external datasets together. However, data linkage across multiple HRDN member sites is generally not supported [28].

DASH has a re3data entry that provides metadata on data licenses, types of access and data uploads permitted, and policy information [29]. However, the entry does not include any information on persistent identifiers, repository certification, metadata standards, quality management, or versioning features [29].

Canadian Research Data Centre Network (CRDCN)

The Canadian Research Data Centre Network (CRDCN) is a partnership between a consortium of Canadian universities and Statistics Canada [30]. In other words, it is a network of data centers/repositories managed by Statistics Canada and hosted at various universities across the country [31].

CRDCN's network provides access to data from Statistics Canada, including the results of many health-related surveys such as the Canadian Community Health Survey [32]. Administrative records from sources such as the Canadian Cancer Registry and the National Ambulatory Care Reporting System are also included [32]. All data within the CRDCN is de-identified [33].

The CRDCN head office is at McMaster University, with over 30 other repositories hosted at other Canadian universities [31], [34]. The primary users of CRDCN are academic and government-based health and social science researchers [35]. However, there is also support for private and international research projects on a case-by-case basis [35].

Data accessibility for academic and government researchers follows a similar four-step process:

1. Confirm the need for Research Data Centre (RDC) data.
2. Submit a project proposal.
3. Obtain either a peer review, a support letter from a supervisor, or a letter from the sponsoring department, depending on the researcher type: faculty, non-faculty, student, or government.
4. Upload documents to the Microdata Access Platform [35].

Researchers affiliated with a university partner generally do not have to pay access fees, while researchers from government agencies usually have to pay a fee [36]. However, core network partners such as the CIHR are exempt [36]. Historically, data has only been accessible by visiting the physical location of an RDC [31]. However, a virtual RDC is actively being rolled out, allowing researchers to access less sensitive data in secure rooms without Statistics Canada staff present and in authorized workstations [37].

CRDCN has a re3data entry that includes policy details, terms of use and license details, types of access and deposits permitted, and information on the metadata standard it follows [38]. The repository does not utilize a persistent identifier system and has not yet been certified [38].

Canadian Primary Care Sentinel Surveillance Network's (CPCSSN) Research Hub

The Canadian Primary Care Sentinel Surveillance Network (CPCSSN) Research Hub functions as Canada's first nationwide data repository specifically designed to hold primary care Electronic Medical Record (EMR) data and make it available for academic research [39]. The data contains structured values such as lab numbers and blood pressure readings without any notes or attachments [39]. This data is extracted, cleaned, coded, and de-identified semi-annually from the EMRs of approximately 1,200 member health providers [39]. CPCSSN respects patient privacy rights and allows patients the option to request that their data not be included in the extracts [40]. The data is then stored at the Centre for Advanced Computing (CAC) at Queen's University [41]. Data within the CPCSSN Research Hub can be linked to administrative data within their respective regional networks [39].

CPCSSN's partners and stakeholders include The College of Family Physicians of Canada, the Public Health Agency of Canada, Queen's University, the [University of Calgary](#), [Dalhousie University](#), the [University of Manitoba](#), and the [University of Alberta](#) [42]. Additional partners include Memorial University of Newfoundland, the University of Ottawa, the University of Toronto, Western University, and the University of British Columbia [42]. The repository also receives funding from a variety of sources, including CIHR, the Departments of Family Medicine, and the Canadian Institute for Military and Veteran Health Research [42].

The primary users of CPCSSN data are academic researchers affiliated with eligible institutions, which include Canadian post-secondary institutions and their associated organizations, such as

hospitals and research centers [39]. However, access is also granted to researchers from non-profit/non-governmental Canadian organizations with clear health research/knowledge transfer mandates and federal or provincial government departments, including regional health authorities [39]. Other organizations are evaluated on a case-by-case basis [39].

While data access requires an approved application and involves service fees ranging from \$5,000 to \$20,000 per project, information regarding data dictionaries, glossaries, and a sample data set is publicly available [39]. Research projects using CPCSSN data typically follow a five-step process:

1. A data access request is submitted with supporting documents.
2. The Data Access Selection Committee reviews the application.
3. If approved, researchers are granted access to the requested data in a Secure Research Environment (SRE).
4. The CPCSSN team provides support for the duration of the access period.
5. The research team requests to extract the analysis results [39].

It is important to note that the CPCSSN is not included in the re3data registry. Therefore, it is not immediately clear which essential metadata elements are used, if any. For example, the repository's use of a persistent identifier system or any data licensing requirements is unknown.

Regional Focused Data Entities

Population Data BC (PopData BC)

Population Data BC (PopData BC) is a repository hosted at the University of British Columbia (UBC) in collaboration with Simon Fraser University and the University of Victoria [43]. The organization's purpose is to serve as a resource for data and education, promoting interdisciplinary research on the factors that influence human health, well-being, and development [44].

To achieve these goals, PopData BC collaborates with numerous federal and provincial organizations that act as data stewards, providing and managing the data [45]. Some of these data stewards are also past or current funders, including BC Cancer, BC Ministry of Citizens' Services, BC Ministry of Health, BC Ministry of Education and Childcare, and WorkSafe BC [46]. Additional partners include The Canadian Urban Environmental Health Research Consortium, Immigration Refugees and Citizenship Canada, The Human Learning Project, Perinatal Services BC, and Statistics Canada [45]. Meanwhile, additional funders include the CIHR, The Human Early Learning Partnership, Health Research BC, the BC Ministry of Small Business, Technology and Economic Development Knowledge Development Fund, and UBC's School of Population and Public Health [46].

Academic researchers can view PopData BC's data, described in detail within a publicly available data catalogue including dataset descriptions, lists of available variables, and notes

about data inclusion and exclusion criteria [47]. However, the access is controlled through the completion of a seven-step data access request (DAR) process that can take six months to a year:

1. The DAR planning: Defining the research question, confirming that the project meets the Five Safes Model, team members meet eligibility criteria, and identifying the desired variables.
2. The DAR is completed and submitted.
3. An appropriate data steward reviews the DAR.
4. Contracts, accounts, and privacy training are completed. The cost is evaluated on a per-project basis and is waived for student researchers doing stand-alone projects.
5. The requested data is provisioned and released to the researcher through an SRE on a private cloud, only accessible via an encrypted VPN.
6. The data is analyzed and goes through a pre-publication review.
7. The project is closed [48].

PopData BC has a re3data entry that contains metadata describing repository size, supported languages, policies, type of data access and uploads permitted, and data licenses [49]. However, there is no evidence of a persistent identifier system, a data quality management process, or that the repository is certified or follows a metadata standard [49].

Health Data Platform BC (HDPBC)

The Health Data Platform BC (HDPBC) is a repository developed by BC's Ministry of Health to facilitate centralized, safe access to health data from contributing partners [50]. While health organizations manage the data, HDPBC provides a platform where the HDPBC team consistently provisions and de-identifies the data [50]. The partners, data contributors, and funders include [PopData BC](#), Fraser Health, Northern Health, Health Research BC, Provincial Health Services, Vancouver Coastal Health, Island Health, Interior Health, and the CIHR [50]. For platform development, HDPBC also collaborates with Swansea University in Wales, UK [50]. The platform's underlying privacy and security framework and data access framework are based on the Five Safes Model - Safe People, Safe Project, Safe Data, Safe Setting, Safe Output [51].

The primary users of HDPBC are researchers, regardless of affiliation, seeking access to health data in British Columbia [52]. For them, the process to request access to data involves four steps:

1. Determine which datasets are needed.
2. Determine the research request type: organizational or academic.
3. Gather necessary information such as documents and other supporting details.
4. Submit a data request application to the HDPBC team or PopData BC [52].

To facilitate feasibility assessments and promote data discoverability, HDPBC maintains a publicly available data catalogue, where each dataset has a description and lists relevant

metadata [53]. This metadata includes the data contributor, the number of tables included in the dataset, the timeframe of the data, the date the data was last updated, and, for some datasets, the frequency that HDPBC refreshes the dataset, a data dictionary, and the record count for the included tables [53].

The data access approval process follows one of three paths [51]:

- **Pre-approved:** All Five Safe criteria are met.
- **Delegate review:** Some but not all requirements are met; an appointed representative reviews the application.
- **Council review:** None of the Five Safe Criteria are met; the application requires full council review.

All approved applications are charged a data access fee starting at \$12,600, with additional optional add-ons such as access to additional historical years, access for more than three users, project amendments, or adding additional computing capabilities [54]. Once the fees are paid and the data is provisioned, researchers gain access to the requested datasets through HDPBC's or PopData BC's SRE, depending on the request type, with the option to bring in and link their own data, subject to approval [54].

Notably, HDPBC does not have a re3data entry. Consequently, the platform's discoverability is limited, and essential metadata information remains undefined. For example, it is uncertain if HDPBC employs a persistent identifier system, complies with established metadata standards, or has implemented clear data licensing guidelines.

University of Alberta Dataverse

As a campus-wide, discipline-agnostic data repository, the University of Alberta (UofA) Dataverse primarily serves UofA faculty, students, and staff, providing them with a platform to store, share, publish, and discover data [55]. Hosted and managed by the UofA Library, the dataverse belongs to the Boralis network and contains over one hundred data deposits from Medicine, Health, and Life Sciences [55].

Anyone with a UofA username can deposit data, selecting from a set of six Creative Commons license options:

- **CC0:** data is entirely in the public domain,
- **CC BY:** others can distribute, remix, adapt, and expand the data, as long as accreditation is given,
- **CC BY-NC:** same as CC BY, but data is restricted to non-commercial use,
- **CC BY-SA:** same as CC BY, with the addition that any new data is licensed under the same terms,
- **CC BY-NC-SA:** same as CC BY-NC, with the addition that new data needs to be licensed under the same terms [56].

As a result, data accessibility varies. Some data is publicly available, while other datasets have restrictions set by the researcher. The UofA Library also offers related data management support, including consultation services and tools such as DMP Assistant, for developing a data management plan, and Archivematica, for preserving data for possible reuse [57], [58], [59].

The University of Alberta Dataverse has a re3data entry that includes metadata on the repository size, supported languages, types of data access and uploads permitted, policies, data licensing guidelines, the use of a persistent identifier system, use of metadata standards, versioning features, and quality management processes [60]. However, there is no evidence of repository certification [60].

PRISM Dataverse - University of Calgary

The PRISM Dataverse is a campus-wide, discipline-agnostic data repository hosted and managed by the University of Calgary (UofC) Library [61]. It serves as a platform for the primary users, UofC faculty, students, and staff to store, share, publish, and discover data [61]. PRISM Dataverse is also a member of the Boralis network and contains over two hundred data deposits from Medicine, Health, and Life Sciences researchers [61].

Anyone with a UofC username can deposit data and select from one of six Creative Commons license options: CC0, CC BY, CC BY-NC, CC BY-SA, and CC BY-NC-SA [56], [62]. Thus, the data accessibility on PRISM Dataverse varies. Some data is publicly available, with restrictions set by the researcher. Related services offered by the library include consultation, new collection setup, dataset reviews, and technical support [63].

While designed primarily for data sharing, data deposits in PRISM Dataverse are retained indefinitely [64]. However, long-term archiving and preservation are not currently offered, meaning continued readability and data accessibility are not guaranteed [64]. The repository has a checksum process to detect file changes, demonstrating at least some evidence of data versioning [64]. Depositors are limited to 5GB files and can deposit any file format, with preference for non-proprietary formats, under the conditions that all sensitive data is anonymized or de-identified and explicit permissions were obtained for sharing Indigenous data and knowledge [63], [64].

PRISM Dataverse's re3data entry includes metadata on repository size, supported languages, types of data access and uploads permitted, policies, data licensing guidelines, a persistent identifier system, metadata standards, and versioning features [65]. However, there is no evidence of quality management processes or repository certification [65].

Health Research Data Platform - Saskatchewan (HRDP-SK)

As learned in a recent webinar, the Health Research Data Platform - Saskatchewan (HRDP-SK) began as an initiative designed to advance healthcare data access for research in Saskatchewan, which was previously fragmented and thus limited Saskatchewan's inclusion in

national studies. Now, the platform's purpose is to ensure that access to Saskatchewan health data is secure, consistent, efficient, and systematic [66]. It is governed by a master health data-sharing agreement signed in 2022 by health system partners and trustees of the original data within Saskatchewan [66].

HRDP-SK contains datasets on province-wide discharges, medical billing, prescription drugs, and administrative health data registries [67]. New datasets are still being added, however, such as those from the mental health and addictions systems, long-term care, and the Saskatchewan Cancer Registry [67]. The main repository datasets come from integrations with Saskatchewan health systems; there is no option for researchers to submit data [68]. However, with proper approvals, researchers are allowed to upload and link other data that will help their analysis [67].

HRDP-SK is a member of the [HRDN](#) and has partnerships with the Saskatchewan Centre for Patient-Oriented Research (SCPOR) and various other organizations, including eHealth Saskatchewan, the University of Saskatchewan, the University of Regina, Saskatchewan Polytechnic, First Nations University of Canada, Saskatchewan Health Research Foundation, Saskatchewan Cancer Agency, Saskatchewan Health Authority, Saskatchewan Health Quality Council, and the Saskatchewan Ministry of Health [66].

The primary users of HRDP-SK are all researchers, regardless of affiliation, seeking access to health data in Saskatchewan [66].

To use the data, researchers must submit an approved access request [69]. A data dictionary and overviews of the datasets are publicly available on the HRDP-SK website to aid in this process [67]. HRDP-SK trustees assess all data access requests. Once approved, researchers can only access their requested data through an SRE [69]. Currently, there are no data access costs; however, there are plans to implement resource recovery costs in January 2026 [69].

The data access process involves seven steps [69]:

1. Feasibility and resource check.
2. Assessments and authorizations.
3. Onboarding and account requests.
4. Accessing and analyzing the data.
5. Output vetting.
6. Sharing results.
7. Project closure.

It is important to note that HRDP-SK does not have a re3data entry. This absence limits the platform's discoverability and leaves key metadata information undefined. For example, whether HRDP-SK employs persistent identifiers, adheres to specific metadata standards, or has established data licensing policies is unclear.

Manitoba Population Research Repository

The Manitoba Population Data Repository is an archive system hosted at the University of Manitoba (UM) and managed by the Manitoba Centre for Health Policy (MCHP) within the Max Rady College of Medicine [70]. The repository provides access to Manitoba government department administrative datasets, encompassing healthcare, social/family care, education, justice, and registries [70]. Its purpose is to support research across various fields, including healthcare, education, social services, and justice. MCHP serves as the data steward, managing the access and maintenance of records and regularly performing data quality evaluations on new and existing datasets [70]. MCHP also maintains a publicly available list of all datasets and associated descriptions [71].

MCHP leverages strategic partnerships to extend the reach and impact of the repository data. Through its membership in the HRDN, data is accessible through the [DASH](#) [70]. MCHP also partners with the Centre for Healthcare Innovation, another UM-affiliated organization that provides services and support in clinical research and methods, data analytics and management, a learning health system, patient and public engagement, and patient-centred measurement [72]. Notably, MCHP's collaborative work with the First Nation Health and Social Secretariat of Manitoba and other members of Spectrum (Social Policy Evaluation Collaborative Team Research at Universities in Manitoba) utilizes the repository data in meaningful research to shape more inclusive, diverse, equitable, and accessible human services, programs, and policies [73]. Spectrum is a partnership between researchers, government staff, and leaders of community organizations [74].

The primary users of this repository are any researchers interested in studying population-based observational data in Manitoba. To access this data, researchers follow these general steps [70]:

1. Attend an accreditation session.
2. Submit a research proposal, project feasibility, and data access quote form.
3. Confirm funding.
4. Obtain privacy and ethics approvals from the Provincial Health Research Privacy Committee, the UM Health Research Ethics Board, and others as necessary.
5. Sign the researcher agreement and submit the required documentation.
6. The analysis plan is developed, and the project starts.
7. Possible project amendments are submitted.
8. Annual project status reports are submitted.
9. Data use and output guidelines are followed during the dissemination phase.
10. The project is closed.

The Manitoba Population Data Repository has a re3data entry that includes information on data repository languages, policies, data license, type of data access and uploads allowed, and an indication that quality management processes are in place [75]. However, the repository does not use a persistent identifier system for the data, there is no evidence of repository certification or any metadata standards used [75]. Notably, the repository is also listed on the Thomson

Reuters Data Citation Index, an alternative data repository search tool [76]. However, that is only available within institutional licenses [76].

Institute for Clinical Evaluative Sciences (ICES) Data Repository

The Institute for Clinical Evaluative Sciences (ICES) is a non-profit research and data services institution that manages a prominent health data repository in Ontario [77]. The head office is within the Sunnybrook Health Sciences Centre/Hospital, with additional locations at Queen's University, University of Ottawa, University of Toronto, Western University, McMaster University, and the Health Sciences North Research Institute [78]. ICES is also partnered with Laurentian University and NOSM University and has many other federal, provincial, local, and Indigenous partnerships [78], [79]. Notably, ICES is also part of the HRDN, with the repository data accessible through the [DASH](#) [79].

The ICES Data Repository contains administrative health data on all Ontarians eligible for provincial health coverage, spanning over thirty years [77]. This includes linked and unlinked datasets such as claims to the Ontario Health Insurance Plan, medical drug claims from the Ontario Drug Benefit Program, hospital discharge summaries from admissions and emergency visits, and claims for long-term care/home care [77]. The repository also includes data from various provincial registries, including the Ontario Cancer Registry, the Ontario Stroke Registry, and the Registry of the Cardiac Network [77]. Researchers accessing this data are allowed to link external datasets, subject to approval [77].

For researchers, ICES datasets are categorized into two groups [77]:

- **Core datasets:** Data that is available to all researchers. This includes the discharge abstract databases, Ontario Drug Benefit Claims, and the Ontario Cancer Registry.
- **Restricted datasets:** Data only available for research projects that meet specific criteria.

The data within both categories is intended for all researchers, both public and private, with an interest in analyzing Ontario health data. While the data dictionary is publicly available on the website, data access is restricted, and the accessibility varies depending on the type of researcher [80], [81]:

- **Public sector researchers**, from academic institutions, hospitals, and non-profit health agencies, can gain access to de-identified record-level data in an SRE or can have the ICES Data and Analytics Services (DAS) team analyze the data on their behalf [82]. The cost for these services varies and is sometimes supported by government funding [82]. The process for public sector researchers involves [82]:
 - Submitting a public sector request to Data & Analytics Services (DAS).
 - Discussing project feasibility, timeline, and cost.
 - Seeking approval from a research ethics board.
 - Signing a DAS agreement.
 - Formulating (with the DAS team) the dataset creation plan.
 - The DAS team creates a cohort for the study.

- Gaining access to an online SRE for analysis and report development with linked record-level data.
- **Private sector researchers** have analysis and aggregation done by the ICES Data and Analytics Services team; no record-level data is available to this group [83]. The cost for these services typically ranges from \$7,000 to \$150,000 [83]. The process for private sector researchers involves [83]:
 - Submitting a private sector services request.
 - Consulting with the DAS team to assess feasibility, eligibility, and timeline.
 - Reviewing and submitting the private sector feasibility form.
 - Signing the DAS private sector agreement.
 - Seeking ethics board approval.
 - Developing a dataset creation plan with DAS.
 - The DAS team performs the analytics and sends preliminary deliverables to the requestor.
 - The DAS team sends the final deliverables and completes the project.

In terms of its metadata and standards, ICES has a re3data entry that includes details on repository size, repository languages, type of data access and data upload permitted, its policies, and data licensing [84]. However, there is no information on the use of a persistent identifier system, and there is no evidence of the repository being certified [84].

McGill University Dataverse

The McGill University Dataverse is an institutional-level repository managed by the university Library and hosted within the Boralis network, a Canadian open-source repository framework [85], [86]. This dataverse serves as a platform for researchers affiliated with McGill to store, share, publish, and discover data [85]. While some data is harvested from other sources, none of this harvested data falls within the categories of health, medicine, or life sciences [85]. Notably, these categories collectively have over 100 data deposits within McGill Dataverse [85].

Given the repository's purpose, the primary users are McGill faculty, students, and staff [85]. In other words, anyone with a McGill account can deposit data and select from one of six Creative Commons license options: CC0, CC BY, CC BY-NC, CC BY-SA, and CC BY-NC-SA [56]. The McGill Dataverse also partners with other university libraries in Quebec through the Partenariat des bibliothèques universitaires du Québec (PBUQ), supporting the availability of Boralis to Quebec researchers [87].

Data accessibility for these users varies. Some data is publicly available, with restrictions set by the researcher through one of the aforementioned license options. Most submissions within the health-related categories are search strategies, code, or results, likely due to the high sensitivity of raw health data [85]. However, additional data is accessible through the COVID-19 Immunity Task Force (CITF) Databank, hosted by McGill's School of Population and Global Health [88]. Access to data in the CITF Data Portal requires a data access application, which goes through an administrative assessment by the data access office and a formal data access committee review [89].

To ensure important metadata is accessible, McGill Dataverse has a re3data entry that includes details on the repository size, repository languages supported (English and French), type of data access and uploads permitted, license information, use of a persistent identifier system, the metadata standards implemented, and the versioning features [90]. However, there is no information on the quality management processes and repository certification [90].

Health Data Nova Scotia (HDNS)

Health Data Nova Scotia (HDNS) is a provincial health data repository hosted and managed by Dalhousie University's Department of Community Health and Epidemiology [91]. The repository provides access to data from Nova Scotia administrative health databases, clinical databases, and survey datasets [92]. HDNS does not accept external submissions, but datasets are internally and externally linkable with approval [92]. Although accessing the data is restricted, some of the metadata is publicly accessible on the HDNS website [92].

HDNS's primary partner is the Maritime SPOR Support Unit (MSSU), a patient-oriented research support organization that collaborates with various data centres in New Brunswick and Nova Scotia [93]. Notably, the HDNS website does not indicate that its data is available through [DASH](#), despite HDNS being an HRDN member [94].

The primary users of this repository are considered to be all researchers, regardless of affiliation, who want to include record-level de-identified data on Nova Scotians [93]. HDNS also works with government bodies, other research institutions, granting agencies, community health boards, and private sector organizations [91].

Access to this data is provided through an SRE and involves a fee [93]. A fee that typically ranges from \$10,000 to \$20,000 per project [95]. The data access process follows a five-step procedure [96]:

1. Initial contact.
2. Complete an access feasibility and cost estimate request.
3. Submit a data access request and a Research Ethics Board application.
4. Sign the contract and confidentiality agreements.
5. Sign the project charter.

Important metadata for HDNS is also publicly available on the HDNS re3data entry [97]. This provides details regarding the type of access and deposit permitted, the license and policy guidelines, and the number of records in the repository, 400 million [97]. However, the repository does not use a persistent identifier system, there is no indication that the data repository is certified or follows any metadata standards, and the quality management process is unknown [97].

Secure Island Data Repository (SIDR)

The Secure Island Data Repository (SIDR) is a repository housed at the University of Prince Edward Island (UPEI) and managed by its Centre for Health and Community Research [98]. SIDR aims to provide secure access to de-identified health data for research and government use in Prince Edward Island (PEI) while fostering collaboration, building research capacity, and promoting ethical data practices, including Indigenous data sovereignty and IDEA (Inclusion, Diversity, Equity, and Accessibility) principles [99]. The data, provided by Health PEI, PEI government departments, and other organizations, is de-identified and linkable, both internally and externally, with approvals [98]. A list of these data holdings is publicly available, however, no dataset-specific metadata information is included [100].

The key stakeholders include UPEI's Department of Health and Wellness, Health PEI, and the New Brunswick Institute for Research, Data and Training [101]. SIDR also collaborates with the Maritime SPOR Support Unit (MSSU) to support Maritimes-focused patient-oriented research, knowledge sharing, and the development of common hosting and data access models for health data in the region [98]. Additionally, the repository is a member of the HRDN, allowing access through the [DASH](#) [98].

Whether an approved data access request was a direct submission or through [DASH](#), SIDR's data holdings are available to all types of researchers via an on-site SRE [102]. While the website indicates plans for future public data availability, current access requires an approved application and involves a project-specific cost [100], [103].

The data access process at SIDR is a 10-step procedure [103]:

1. Define the research question.
2. Determine the required data.
3. Schedule a consultation appointment with SIDR.
4. Complete a feasibility form.
5. Complete the remainder of the data access application package.
6. Obtain project approvals, including from the SIDR Data Release Committee, UPEI Privacy review, and the PEI Research Ethics Board.
7. Review the quote and sign the data access agreement.
8. Complete required administrative safeguards, including privacy training, a confidentiality agreement, and security orientation.
9. Finalize the data creation plan.
10. Access the approved data.

In terms of discoverability and transparency, SIDR does not have a re3data entry. Consequently, key information about its data management practices remains unclear. For instance, details regarding persistent identifier usage, adherence to metadata standards, and licensing policies are not readily available.

Discussion

This review of key entities within the Canadian health data landscape reveals that the Canadian health data ecosystem is diverse, with varying maturity levels in data management and access processes. Several common themes and notable differences emerge from the analysis.

Highlighting the variability in repository characteristics across the Canadian health data landscape, Table 1 summarizes key attributes drawn from "Common Descriptive Attributes of Research Data Repositories" by the Research Data Alliance's Data Repository Attributes Working Group. A white paper that identifies essential metadata for understanding these resources [104]. The metadata elements used in this summary are: Repository Name, URL, Organization(s), Research Area, Persistent Identifiers (PID) system, Terms of Deposit, and Terms of Access. Other metadata described in the RDA paper that were taken into consideration were Country and Description. However, since this landscape analysis is limited to Canada, instead of analyzing the Country, Table 1 is split into two sections: Pan-Canadian Data Repositories, Regional Data Repositories. Additionally, the Description was not included in Table 1, given that thorough details of each repository can be found in each of their respective sections above. While not included in the RDA report, Table 1 also includes a column, re3data Entry, to highlight which of the data repositories are listed on re3data.org.

Table 1: Data Repository Descriptive Attribute Summary

Repository Name & URL	Organization(s)	Research Area	PID System	Terms of Deposit	Terms of Access	re3data Entry
Pan-Canadian Data Repositories						
Canadian Institute for Health Information Repository (https://www.cihi.ca/en/access-data-and-reports)	Canadian Institute for Health Information	Health system performance and population health	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Restricted	Open and restricted	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Canada Health Infoway Dataverse (https://borealisdata.ca/dataverse/canadahealthinfoway)	Canada Health Infoway, University of Victoria	Health innovation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	restricted	open	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Canadian Open Neuroscience Platform Portal (https://portal.conp.ca/)	Many funders, including Brain Canada Foundation, Ontario Brain Institute, UofC	Neuroscience	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	open	Open and restricted	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Canadian Research Data Centre Network (https://crdcn.ca/publications-data/data/)	Funded by Canadian Foundation for Innovation, CIHR, and SSHRC, hosted at McMaster University	Government	<input type="checkbox"/>	restricted	Open and restricted	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Canadian Primary Care Sentinel Surveillance Network Research Hub (https://cpcssn.ca/researchhub/)	Canadian Primary Care Sentinel Surveillance Network and Queen's University	Health research	<input type="checkbox"/>	restricted	restricted	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regional Data Repositories						
Population Data BC (https://www.popdata.bc.ca/data)	University of British Columbia, Simon Fraser University, and the University of Victoria	Determinants of health, well-being, and development	<input type="checkbox"/>	restricted	restricted	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Health Data Platform BC (https://healthdataplatformbc.ca/welcome-health-data-platform-bc)	BC Ministry of Health	Health research	<input type="checkbox"/>	restricted	restricted	<input type="checkbox"/>
University of Alberta Dataverse	University of Alberta	Institutional	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	restricted	open	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

(https://borealisdata.ca/dataverse/ualberta)						
PRISM Dataverse (https://borealisdata.ca/dataverse/calgary)	University of Calgary	Institutional	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	restricted	open	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Health Research Data Platform - Saskatchewan (https://www.scpor.ca/hrdpsk)	Saskatchewan Centre for Patient-Oriented Research, University of Saskatchewan	healthcare	<input type="checkbox"/>	restricted	restricted	<input type="checkbox"/>
Manitoba Population Research Repository (https://umanitoba.ca/manitoba-centre-for-health-policy/data-repository)	Manitoba Centre for Health Policy, University of Manitoba	healthcare	<input type="checkbox"/>	restricted	restricted	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ICES Data Repository (https://www.ices.on.ca/)	Government and academic	healthcare	<input type="checkbox"/>	restricted	restricted	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
McGill University Dataverse (https://borealisdata.ca/dataverse/mcgill)	McGill University	Institutional	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	restricted	open	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Health Data Nova Scotia (https://medicine.dal.ca/departments/dep)	Dalhousie University	healthcare	<input type="checkbox"/>	restricted	restricted	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

artment-sites/ community-he alth/research/ hdns.html)						
Secure Island Data Repository (https://sidrpei.ca/)	Centre for Health and Community Research, University of Prince Edward Island	healthcare	<input type="checkbox"/>	restricted	restricted	<input type="checkbox"/>

Data accessibility for researchers is consistently emphasized across the entities. Most organizations facilitate data access to support research and improve healthcare outcomes. However, the level of access varies significantly. While some, like CPCSSN and HRDP-SK, utilize SREs to protect data, others, such as PRISM Dataverse and the University of Alberta Dataverse, offer more direct data downloads with researcher-defined restrictions. This variation highlights the need for a nuanced approach to balancing data accessibility with privacy and security considerations. Furthermore, the approach to data discoverability varies across the entities, with differences in the availability and detail of data catalogues.

The role of partnerships and collaborations is another prominent feature of the Canadian health data landscape. Many entities actively engage with various stakeholders, including government agencies, academic institutions, and research networks, such as the BC Ministry of Health, the University of Calgary, and HRDN. These collaborations are crucial for data sharing, resource pooling, and advancing interdisciplinary research. However, the level and nature of these partnerships differ. While some entities, like DASH and PopData BC, are fundamentally built on collaboration, others, such as individual university data repositories, have a more localized focus.

Metadata practices and adherence to data management standards also present a mixed picture. As shown in Table 1, some repositories, such as the Canadian Open Neuroscience Platform Portal and the University of Alberta Dataverse, demonstrate a commitment to metadata standards and have a PID system implemented. While other repositories, such as SIDR and HRDP-SK, lack re3data entries and provide limited information about their metadata practices. This inconsistency poses challenges for data interoperability and reuse, hindering the development of a truly integrated national health data ecosystem. The absence of widespread repository certification further raises concerns about data quality assurance and long-term preservation.

Overall, the Canadian health data ecosystem demonstrates some strengths, particularly in its commitment to supporting research and fostering collaboration. However, there are also areas for significant improvement. Furthermore, the future of this ecosystem has the potential to be shaped by new repositories still under development, such as Archimedes [105]. As highlighted in a recent conversation with Marc Albert, this health data platform aims to provide a Canadian repository that is a centralized and federated curation of heart and brain data. The access levels

will range from fully open to entirely controlled through an access request process. Addressing the challenges and supporting these developments will be crucial for maximizing the impact of Canadian health data and ensuring its FAIR use in all Canadian health research.

Recommendations

To maximize the impact of Canadian health data and ensure its FAIR use in existing and emerging repositories, including Archimedes, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Expand the scope of analysis:** This analysis should be continued to incorporate other Canadian health-focused entities. Due to limitations in knowledge and time, the current review was unable to include all relevant organizations and regions. Notably, Yukon, Northwest Territories, Nunavut, Quebec, New Brunswick, and Newfoundland and Labrador were not represented as no regional health-focused data holdings in these areas were found. This may be due to infrastructure limitations, but further research is needed to confirm.
2. **Promote enhanced health data management practices:** Actively promote and support the adoption of best practices in data management, including:
 - a. Metadata standards, such as Dublin Core and DDI
 - b. Persistent identifiers, such as DOIs, to improve data interoperability and reuse.
 - c. Data repository certification, such as the CoreTrust Seal, to enhance data quality assurance and long-term preservation.
3. **Standardize Data Access Procedures:** Develop national or regional guidelines for standardized data access procedures, balancing the need for data security with the goal of facilitating efficient research access.

The World Data System (WDS) can play a crucial role in supporting the implementation of these recommendations. For example, the WDS can facilitate knowledge sharing among Canadian health data entities and connect them to international best practices in data management. This can be achieved by increasing awareness of the WDS within the health research community and promoting the benefits of becoming a WDS member. Additionally, the WDS can advocate for a wider adoption of international standards related to metadata, persistent identifiers, and repository certification, thereby enhancing the interoperability and trustworthiness of Canadian health data resources.

Conclusion

This landscape analysis has provided an extensive overview of the Canadian health data ecosystem, highlighting both its strengths and areas for improvement. The analysis underscores the critical importance of open science principles and robust data management practices for maximizing the impact of Canadian health data. By addressing the identified challenges and implementing the proposed recommendations, particularly with the support of organizations like the World Data System, Canada can further advance its capacity for FAIR data and effective health research, ultimately benefiting the health and well-being of all Canadians.

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